

A methodology for dynamic procurement of secondary reserve capacity in power systems with significant vRES penetrations

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Abstract— The European pathway to carbon neutrality indicates strong investments in variable renewable energy sources. Demand-side and variable renewable players rely on forecasts to participate in day-ahead markets closing between 12 and 37 hours ahead of real-time operation. As such, the further from the real-time operation those forecasts are provided, the higher their errors and the uncertainty. Deviations from the market schedules are balanced using real-time reserves. Traditionally, transmission system operators (TSOs) use a symmetrical procurement of up and down reserves based on the expected demand. This work considers the computation of a dynamic up and down procurement of secondary capacities by considering the expected deviations, using the day-ahead programmed and expected dispatches of variable renewables, demand, other technologies, and the cross-border capacities. The study uses operational open data from the Spanish TSO from 2019 to 2022. The proposed methodology allows increasing the usage of the up and down secondary capacities by almost 13% and 8%, respectively, freeing up 11% of the allocated resources, on average.

Index Terms-- balancing markets, dynamic secondary capacity procurement, forecast uncertainty, programmed dispatch.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 2030 European National Energy and Climate Plans indicate sector coupling and a high investment in variable renewable energy sources (vRES), such as wind and solar photovoltaic (PV) technologies to achieve the goal of a carbon-neutral society by 2050 [1],[2]. Increasing penetrations of vRES are raising the usage and costs of reserves across Europe due to their stochastic production profile [3],[4]. The duck curve effect originated from high penetration of solar PV is already a reality in several power systems with significant up and down net load ramps (load minus vRES generation). This situation leads to the so-called merit-order effect, which reduces market prices in the case of negative or nearly zero net loads and increases balancing costs in the case of net load ramps [5],[6]. Market

participants pay the balancing costs of their imbalances as Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs) [7],[8]. The self-cannibalization effect and the increase in balancing costs originated by increasing penetrations of vRES are obstacles for their market integration without externalities like support schemes [9],[10]. Demand-side and vRES players rely on forecasts to participate in electricity markets. These forecasts tend to have higher uncertainty, especially in time horizons farther from the real-time operation [8],[11].

The European Single Day-ahead Coupling market is the most liquid electricity market, closing between 12 and 37 hours ahead of real-time operation. TSOs use the day-ahead market (DAM) outputs to define the programmed dispatches of each player. After its closure, TSOs have to define the required capacities of the Frequency Restoration Reserves (FRR) needed to cover potential real-time deviations from programmed schedules [12],[13]. While the DAM rules are harmonized in Europe, the rules of balancing markets (BMs) significantly differ among different market zones [13]. Traditionally, TSOs use a symmetrical procurement of up and down automatic FRR (aFRR), also known as secondary reserves, based on the expected demand, as suggested by the European Network of TSOs (ENTSO-E). The Spanish and Portuguese TSOs use a practically symmetrical and an asymmetrical procurement of secondary reserves, respectively [14]. In those secondary capacity markets, participants need to be able to provide an interval of down and up capacity to support this balancing mechanism. So, markets with high penetration values of vRES shall adapt their design according to the stochastic behavior of vRES. These changes to market designs shall integrate vRES and increase the operational efficiency of power systems [13]-[17].

The legislation of the European Commission for regulating the European Internal Market of Electricity (EIME) encompasses measures of market design and harmonization

aiming at increasing the efficiency of the procurement of secondary capacity. It suggests the dynamic separate procurement of up and down capacity to increase competition and allocation efficiency [13]. Naturally, by dividing the market by procurement of down and up capacity, more players can participate, increasing competition. Some studies consider the dynamic allocation of secondary capacity considering historical data [4],[18]-[20]. De Vos et al. considered a machine learning approach to estimate imbalance uncertainty aiming at changing the size of the Belgium operating reserves from a yearly to a daily basis, decreasing it by 5% [21]. Kruse, Schäfer and Without presented an ex-post machine learning approach to size secondary reserves. They identified the variables that better estimates the error, being that crucial to detect when secondary control is activated [22]. Furthermore, to increase the allocation efficiency of cross-border capacity when exchanging balancing services, the legislation suggested coupling BMs, as observed in the Nordpool market [14][23].

The work presented in this paper aims to analyse the benefits of considering an asymmetrical dynamic capacity procurement of secondary reserves, using the Spanish power system as a case study. The study used operational open data from the Spanish TSO, which eased its replication. The data considers the gate closure of each market in Spain. The secondary capacity market closes on the day-ahead, after the clearing of the day-ahead (DA) market. Typically, TSOs acquire extraordinary reserves from bilateral agreements with providers, which may increase their costs. Against this background, after analyzing the lack of secondary capacity usage and its extraordinary capacity needs in Portugal and Spain, it is possible to conclude that the methodologies used to define the secondary capacity needs are inefficient [24]. The presented work considers the computation of a dynamic up and down procurement of secondary capacities by considering the expected deviations, using the day-ahead programmed and expected dispatches of vRES, demand, other power sources, and the cross-border capacities. The open-access Multi-agent Trading of Renewable Production (RESTrade) tool was used to test the application of this methodology in Spain [25].

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II presents an overview of wholesale and balancing electricity markets. Section III presents the methodologies for procurement of secondary capacity with the formulation of the new methodology. Section IV presents two case studies. Finally, concluding remarks are presented in Section V.

II. ELECTRICITY MARKETS

The legislation of the EIME encompasses measures of market harmonization that can motivate the integration of vRES and the demand side, incentivizing their active participation in electricity markets [13]. Wholesale markets are composed of long-term derivative and bilateral markets, short-term marginal day-ahead and intraday markets, close to real-time continuous pay-as-bid intraday markets, and real-time ancillary services [26]. While derivatives and bilateral contracts are used for risk hedging, DAMs are the main energy trading [27]. Intraday markets allow agents to correct potential energy deviations closer to real-time [28]. Ancillary services solve real-time grid

congestion and frequency and voltage oscillations, among other issues. Deviations from schedules are compensated in BMs, and the BRPs that deviate may need to pay the imbalance prices. While the harmonization process of day-ahead and intraday markets is at an advanced stage, BMs are still in the beginning. In most European markets, BMs are mandatory and imposed by ENTSO-E to guarantee the power reserve values within each control zone. In Europe, there are three key types of load-frequency control used to balance power systems. During real-time operation, the primary or frequency control reserve (FCR) is the first to be activated after frequency oscillations in a few seconds. The secondary, or aFRR, and the tertiary, or manually activated FRR (mFRR), are used to free up FCR and aFRR in a maximum of 5 and 15 minutes, respectively [13][29].

The efficient exchange of balancing services is the principal element of the adopted Electricity Balancing Guideline (EBG) [30]. However, the European level of discrepancy between the adopted four and seven schemes for procuring balancing energy in the secondary and tertiary reserves is high, respectively [8]. This issue caused substantial differences in the overall costs of the balancing services and the imbalance prices between the European countries. The low efficiency of using cross-border exchanges of balancing services can be explained by the lack of progress observed in the integration of BMs, by the national market characteristics due to their importance for a secure and stable operation of the power system, and the necessity of interventions by TSOs. Nordpool countries are the few sharing BMs. In Iberia, Portugal and Spain share the wholesale electricity markets (MIBEL) but have their own BMs. They only exchange some extraordinary balancing services through bilateral agreements [14]. Furthermore, the formulation to compute imbalance prices differs in several systems [31]. The EIME legislation has clear rules, equal to everyone, incentivizing the fair payment of deviations by BRPs. Improving these aspects of harmonization related to pricing mechanisms, schemes, and imbalance price formulations are the main challenges to implementing the EBG. These issues are also referred to in the EIME legislation for BMs, stating the separate procurement between balancing energy and capacity, the maximum use and efficient allocation of the cross-zonal capacity, the exclusive use of the marginal pricing methodology, and the settlement of imbalance prices that reflect the real-time value of energy can improve the efficient use of BMs [31]. The reduction in the electricity prices, originated by the vRES, can be an issue for future non-discriminatory integration of these sources in the electricity markets as active market players, once without feed-in tariffs, other incentives, or changes in the market design, maybe no attractiveness for future investments in these sources.

A. Iberian Secondary balancing markets

Portugal and Spain participate in the Iberian Market of Electricity (MIBEL), which consists of bilateral, derivatives, and spot markets. Ancillary services are independent and managed by each country TSO. For frequency control, they consider the European balancing guidelines of the ENTSO-E with the following characteristics [8],[29],[30].

All technically capable players may participate in the yearly capability auctions for secondary control. Therefore, they must support secondary control throughout the year. Portugal and Spain consider day-ahead hourly marginal auctions of secondary capacity. For historical reasons, the Portuguese TSO requires an asymmetrical secondary capacity band with an up capacity that doubles the down capacity. It uses the ENTSO-E guidelines, upscaling the up capacity by 60% and downscaling the down capacity until 40%. So, to participate in secondary, players must automatically respond in milliseconds and be capable of providing both down-regulation and up-regulation, bidding an up capacity that doubles the down capacity [14],[30]. The price of the energy in the secondary reserve is defined by the tertiary market (if cleared) or by the regulator due to the lack of competition. As most players providing secondary control are combined cycle gas turbines, the regulator defines the price of this service as the marginal cost of this technology [15]. In Spain, the procurement of secondary capacity is practically symmetrical, being its real-time balancing energy procured considering the typical pay-as-cleared mechanism of marginal markets [14],[29]. When secondary capacities obtained from competitive marginal markets are not enough to guarantee the secure operation of power systems, extraordinary reserves are acquired from bilateral agreements or in the tertiary market [14]. Furthermore, Portugal and Spain bilaterally exchange ancillary services to comply with small unbalances in their cross-border exchanges [8],[12],[14].

III. DYNAMIC PROCUREMENT OF SECONDARY CAPACITY

RETrade tool comprises the models of the traditional hourly power and energy reserve markets. It supports the participation of vRES and demand players in the system balance, i.e., secondary and tertiary reserve markets. Also, it may use both the marginal pricing theory and the pay-as-bid scheme to define prices. All technically capable players shall submit their availability to support the secondary control every year. Further, they must submit capacity bids to the marginal secondary capacity market. Depending on the market structure and rules, if allocated to provide secondary capacity, players may have to submit up and down energy bids to a secondary energy market. Furthermore, if automatically dispatched to provide secondary control they will receive the marginal cost of the: i) secondary energy market (if exists); ii) tertiary energy market (if cleared); iii) defined technology by the Regulator.

The aFRR capacity, C_t , consider the balancing guidelines of the ENTSO-E concerning a symmetrical procurement of down, C_t^{down} , and up, C_t^{up} , capacities based on the expected maximum consumption, \hat{E}_t^{Lmax} , per time period t , as follows:

$$C_t = C_t^{down} = C_t^{up} = \sqrt{a\hat{E}_t^{Lmax} + b^2} - b \quad (1)$$

Where a and b are constants equal to 10 and 150, respectively. Similarly, it is also possible to use the asymmetrical Portuguese procurement of reserves:

$$C_t^{up} = p \times \sqrt{a\hat{E}_t^{Lmax} + b^2} - b \quad (2)$$

$$C_t^{down} = C_t^{up} / 2 \quad (3)$$

Where p is a constant that varies between 1.2 and 1.6 according with the hour of the day.

The market dynamics shall be considered to compute the separate dynamic capacity procurement of up and down secondary capacities. Naturally, consumption keeps influencing the balancing needs, as suggested by the previous two procurement methodologies. However, with sector coupling, self-consumption, and increasing penetrations of vRES, consumption tends to be more flexible and follows market dynamics. So, instead of using the expected maximum consumption as in the old-fashioned methodologies, the expected day-ahead consumption, E_t^L , can be used. Furthermore, has been considered the day-ahead programmed dispatches of all generators, E_t^G , vRES, E_t^V , and net cross-border trades, E_t^C . These variables are important for detecting if the day-ahead programmed dispatches are similar to the day-ahead expected consumption and generation. So, the expected day-ahead deviations from schedules, $\nabla \hat{E}_t^D$, consider those variables and the expected solar PV, \hat{E}_t^S , and wind production, \hat{E}_t^W , considering the expected last, $\nabla \hat{E}_{t,t-1}^D$, and next period deviations, $\nabla \hat{E}_{t+1,t}^D$, as presented in formulations (5) and (6). On their daily operation, when computing the secondary capacity procurement for hour 23 (t), TSOs do not know the day-ahead dispatch of hour 24 ($t+1$), assuming the same of hour 23 (t).

Using the expected solar PV and wind production computed by the TSOs is very important to detect potential secondary needs. As multiple players bid for their single or small aggregated vRES, their forecast errors are substantially higher than the ones of TSOs. Furthermore, it is important to consider the expected deviations in previous ($t-1$) and following ($t+1$) time steps since secondary control is activated only to eliminate very short-run deviations. So, if it is expected to have deviations stable from one period to another, the tertiary control needs to be activated. The possibility of also considering the error between the day-ahead cleared and expected demand was also considered in this approach. However, demand-side players tend to adjust deviations closer to real-time operation, compared with vRES.

In the case of deviations, it is also important to identify the expected programmed dispatch of generators between periods, $\nabla E_{t,t-1}^G$, to evaluate if they can mitigate or increase deviations, formulation (7). Multiple variables have been considered but the ones presented in formulations (4)-(8) revealed to be the key drivers to detect the secondary needs and improve their procurement. In this sense, a multi linear regression analysis is applied to the hourly up and down secondary capacities considering all potential operational variables that may affect secondary needs, as follows:

$$C_t^{up} = \max(0; \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 E_t^L + \alpha_2 E_t^V + \alpha_3 E_t^G + \alpha_4 E_t^C + \alpha_5 \nabla \hat{E}_{t,t-1}^D + \alpha_6 \nabla \hat{E}_{t+1,t}^D + \alpha_7 \nabla E_{t+1,t}^G) \quad (4)$$

$$\nabla \hat{E}_{t,t-1}^D = E_t^L + E_{t-1}^V + E_{t-1}^G + E_{t-1}^C + \hat{E}_t^S + \hat{E}_t^W - E_{t-1}^L - E_{t-1}^V - E_{t-1}^G - E_{t-1}^C - \hat{E}_{t-1}^S - \hat{E}_{t-1}^W \quad (5)$$

$$\nabla \hat{E}_{t+1,t}^D = E_{t+1}^L + E_t^V + E_t^G + E_t^C + \hat{E}_{t+1}^S + \hat{E}_{t+1}^W - E_t^L - E_{t+1}^V - E_{t+1}^C - \hat{E}_t^S - \hat{E}_t^W \quad (6)$$

$$\nabla E_{t,t-1}^G = E_t^G - E_{t-1}^G \quad (7)$$

$$C_t^{\text{down}} = \max(0; \beta_0 + \beta_1 E_t^L + \beta_2 E_t^V + \beta_3 E_t^G + \beta_4 E_t^C + \beta_5 \nabla \hat{E}_{t,t-1}^D + \beta_6 \nabla \hat{E}_{t+1,t}^D + \beta_7 \nabla E_{t+1,t}^G) \quad (8)$$

Where α and β are the regression coefficients. The max function is added to avoid negative values. The following section tests the methodology developed for dynamic procurement of down and up secondary capacity.

IV. STUDY

This section is divided into two studies. First, has been used REStTrade to simulate the Spanish BMs in 2019, evaluating potential issues. Then, REStTrade is used to compute the dynamic capacity procurement in Spain during 2019-2022, comparing its outputs with the methodology used by the TSO.

A. Spanish balancing results in 2019

In 2019, the share of renewable generation and vRES in the Spanish demand was slightly 40% and 26%, respectively (check [24] for more details). The balancing energy share in the demand was 3.1%, while its share of the secondary reserves balancing capacity in the total demand was 3.8%. It allocated more secondary capacity than the total energy needed to balance the system. Increasing shares of vRES increases the uncertainty and therefore the need for reserve capacity. If its reserve procurement is not adapted to high shares of vRES, the tendency is to increase its balancing energy share in the total demand. This means that its procurement for secondary capacity is inefficient, which can be confirmed by its usage of the allocated secondary capacities of 27.7%. These values are reflected in the penalties paid by BRPs, around 20.3% of the wholesale market price. REStTrade is used to compute the dynamic procurement of down and up secondary capacities in Spain for 2022 using formulations (4)-(8). They have been computed considering the operational Spanish data of the expected deviations, using the day-ahead (DA) programmed and expected dispatches of vRES, demand, other producers, and the cross-border lines.

B. Characterization of the Spanish procurement for secondary capacity and energy from 2019 to 2022

This study tests the developed methodology for dynamic procurement of secondary capacity. Using the DA forecast and dispatch data from 2019 to 2022, it is possible to verify that the Spanish TSO only used 22% and 37% of the allocated up and down secondary reserves, respectively. Furthermore, it is possible to verify that there was a need for 3% and 7% of extraordinary secondary reserves due to a lack of allocated up and down capacities, respectively. Table I presents the main values, e.g., the standard deviation (Stdev), of the variables under study during the period from 2019 to 2022 in Spain [32]. Analysing Table I it is verified that the mean usage of the allocated up and down capacities during the studied period was 22% and 37%, respectively.

TABLE I: STUDIED VARIABLES DURING 2019-2022.

Variable	Analysis			
	Mean	Stdev	Min	Max
Up Capacity (MW)	624	152	419	958
Up Energy (MWh)	137	171	0	1655
Extraordinary Up Energy (MWh)	138	135	0.4	923
Down Capacity (MW)	543	126	363	946
Down Energy (MWh)	200	212	0	1721
Extraordinary Down Energy (MWh)	165	278	0.5	633
Hourly Capacity (MW)	1166	247	1166	1890
DA Demand forecast (MWh)	27605	4476	14170	41773
Scheduled DA vRES (MWh)	9176	4379	775	26814
Scheduled DA Production (MWh)	26962	4733	13340	41299
Scheduled DA Tie Lines (MWh)	-152	2339	-7113	6770
DA Wind forecast (MWh)	6374	3650	139	20879
DA PV forecast (MWh)	2051	2893	0	12203
$\nabla \hat{E}_{t,t-1}^D$ (MWh)	0	514	-5556	5177
$\nabla \hat{E}_{t+1,t}^D$ (MWh)	0	622	-5556	5885
$\nabla E_{t,t-1}^G$ (MWh)	0	1193	-6821	6285

In relative terms, the usage of the down secondary capacity is superior because the TSO allocated it less but activated it more during the studied period. Furthermore, it is verified that there was a need for 3% (154 GWh) and 7% (463 GWh) of extraordinary secondary reserves with 1104 (3%) and 2801 (8%) occurrences due to a lack of allocated up and down capacities (these extraordinary needs were computed by multiplying the average needs with the number of occurrences, being the relative values their division by the total up and down balancing energy, respectively). The extraordinary energy is acquired through bilateral agreements or in the tertiary market. Because of the lack of information about its costs, this study aims at increasing the usage of secondary allocation, not surpassing its historical extraordinary needs during the studied period. Table II presents the cross-correlation of the allocated up and down secondary capacities and their required energy.

TABLE II: CROSS-CORRELATION OF THE MAIN VARIABLES.

Variable	Cross-Correlation			
	Up Capacity	Up energy	Down Capacity	Down Energy
Up Capacity		0.01	0.59	0.14
Up Energy	0.01		0.01	-0.52
Down Capacity	0.59	0.01		0.21
Down Energy	0.14	-0.52	0.21	

Analysing Table II, it is possible to justify the low usage of up secondary capacity by its practically no correlation with the up energy. Naturally, the correlation between up and down

capacities is high according to the practically symmetrical methodology employed by the Spanish TSO. However, there is an inverse correlation between up and down energy, which supports the inefficiency of the actual methodology, and the need to dynamically allocate secondary capacity.

C. Dynamic capacity procurement in 2022

The allocation proposed in this work applies a regression to the hourly up and down secondary capacities considering the presented operational variables that may affect them during the period 2019-2021 (calibration period) to be used in 2022 (validation period): day-ahead programmed schedules of all production, vRES production, and tie-lines energy flows, and forecasts of demand, wind, and solar PV, as presented in formulations (4)-(8) and Table III.

TABLE III: COEFFICIENTS OF THE REGRESSION ANALYSIS.

Outputs	Regression Analysis	
	Up Reserves	Down Reserves
Intercept (MW)	632.457	-226.097
DA Demand forecast (MWh)	-0.021	0.016
Scheduled DA vRES (MWh)	0.015	-0.011
Scheduled DA Production (MWh)	0.001	0.007
Scheduled DA Tie Lines (MWh)	0.006	-0.008
$\nabla \hat{E}_{t,t-1}^D$ (MWh)	-0.016	0.030
$\nabla \hat{E}_{t+1,t}^D$ (MWh)	0.001	-0.011
$\nabla \hat{E}_{t,t-1}^G$ (MWh)	-0.003	0.007

From Table III it is possible to conclude that all analyzed variables that are contributing to increasing up reserves are then contributing to decreasing down reserves, such as the opposite, which is aligned with the historical negative correlation between them. Thus, instead of having two symmetrical allocations of up and down capacity is possible to adapt them according to expected needs.

Table IV presents the main results of the study.

TABLE IV: MAIN ESTIMATED AND (OBSERVED) VALUES IN 2022.

Variables	Analysis			
	Mean	Stdev	Min	Max
Up Capacity (MW)	633 (726)	74 (148)	414 (452)	883 (945)
Down Capacity (MW)	635 (690)	138 (162)	237 (377)	1042 (946)
Hourly Capacity (MW)	1268 (1415)	134 (290)	913 (862)	1609 (1890)
Extraordinary Up Energy (MWh)	162 (158)	168 (156)	0.04 (~0.40)	955 (855)
Extraordinary Down Energy (MWh)	155 (174)	153 (156)	0.21 (0.50)	828 (969)

From Table IV it is possible to conclude that compared with the existing methodology the mean allocation capacities were reduced by almost 13% and 8% for up and down capacities, freeing up 11% of the hourly resources, on average. Also, the minimum and maximum allocated capacities reduced without affecting the total magnitude of the extraordinary secondary

energy needs. However, their maximum values increased for up energy but reduced for down energy. Compared with the existing formulation, a reduction of 3 occurrences in extraordinary upward energy was identified. Conversely, an increase of 59 events was identified for downward extraordinary balancing needs. Table V presents the cross-correlation analysis after the application of the dynamic procurement of secondary capacity.

TABLE V: CROSS-CORRELATION OF THE MAIN VARIABLES.

Variable	Cross-Correlation			
	Up Capacity	Up energy	Down Capacity	Down Energy
Up Capacity		0.18	-0.33	-0.14
Up Energy	0.18		-0.13	-0.52
Down Capacity	-0.33	-0.13		0.24
Down Energy	-0.14	-0.52	0.24	

Analysing Table V can be verified that the correlation between allocated capacity and used energy is higher and closer to the real-time needs of TSOs to balance power systems. Also, up and down capacity allocations are inversely correlated, freeing up, on average, 11% of the resources for the right balance direction needs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This article presented some of the employed methodologies to allocate secondary balancing capacity in Europe. Furthermore, it presented a new dynamic methodology to allocate capacity by considering expected future deviations. It presented the allocation of secondary capacity in Spain in 2022 using data from 2019 to 2021.

Using RESTrade tool it has been verified that the usage of up and down allocated capacities was only 22% and 37%, respectively. The employed dynamic allocation of secondary capacity allows for increasing the usage of the allocated up and down capacities by almost 13% and 8%, respectively, and freeing up 11% of resources when they are not needed. In addition, a decrease of 3 occurrences in extraordinary upward balancing needs was identified, while an increase of 59 events was observed in the case of downward needs.

Future work aims to test the performance of different capacity allocation methodologies (e.g., machine learning approaches) and additional operational variables, especially to address extreme situations, ensuring the reliability of the power system. With the existing electricity market designs, the expected high shares of vRES in coming years will increase the uncertainty of the balancing needs. The results from this work support the need to adapt current methodologies to enhance the efficiency of the capacity allocation and accommodate the intrinsic features of vRES.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under project TradeRES (grant agreement No 864276).

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